

Internet of Things based Monitoring and Control of Climatic Environment for Greenhouse

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ABSTRACT

This paper focuses on producing a controlled greenhouse atmosphere to promote plant viability. The ESP8266 Node MCU module is used in several different ways to assess the climate behavior within the heating zone and to manage the parameters related to the development of the crops. This is done by employing the most affordable, adaptable green module. The factors that must be taken into account include the moisture content of the soil, field temperature, humidity of the field, and the barriers that plants erect to restrict its growth. The plan, calls for the monitoring of the ground moisture sensor, LDR sensor, DHT11 sensor, and PIR sensor. The majority of these sensors gather data and send it to the Node MCU module, where it is processed before being used to control the devices like water pump, motor, exhaust system, and lighting device. The Node MCU module is connected to IoT (Internet of Things) forums that support feature communication with Wi-Fi internet connection aided with HTTP protocol. No matter how far away farmers are, they can use an IoT platform to collect environmental data in an online mode to their smartphones so they can accomplish the things they should leave undone on rural farms. The age has advanced swiftly and is still evolving in its own special way in the domains of food cultivation and production, benefiting more crops that thrive in agriculture.

Keywords: Greenhouse, Internet of Things (IoT), Node MCU ESP8266 Module, Sensors, ThingSpeak™.

INTRODUCTION

Agricultural production of a country is crucial and its prosperity on a global stage. Agriculture and technology working together will produce better results in yielding crop. There are issues with conventional farming, such as crop disease and changing weather conditions that harm the production. As a result, the agricultural method should be contemporary and the support on crops should be sustainable, as is done in many worldwide locales. This paper proposes a sort of low-cost routine that uses wireless communication Node MCU ESP8266 [1] for short distances and consumes low power. System on chip kit called Node MCU ESP8266 which has a Wi-Fi module and it gets data from sensors. These sensors [1, 2] will gather information like temperature, humidity and other parameters to sustain greenhouse environment by linking with farmers through IoT platform.

Related Study:

José A. Aznar-Sánchez, et.al. [3] have developed a system to analyze worldwide scientific achievements in greenhouse technology for the past 2 decades, aiming to pinpoint the key factors, the most notable study areas, and any gaps in the body of knowledge. Study results reveals that different aspects of greenhouse farming, such as the use of irrigation systems, the development of the best greenhouse framework, the preservation of land for ideal growing situations, the system's overall energy consumption, ventilation systems inside the plant, and insect control were the present greenhouse controlled environment research.

Yajie Liu [4] article explains the implementation and setup of an IoT-enabled greenhouse automation structure that allows worldwide parameter monitoring and management. The greenhouse prototype described here, monitors and regulates three crucial greenhouse system parameters including temperature, water content of the soil and greenhouse light intensity. For better monitoring and analysis, the variation in each sensor's data over time can be visually represented. Proposed project can be implemented in botanical gardens. Possibility of deployment of temperature monitoring and control actions at house spaces such as conference rooms and seminar halls.

Vishwakarma, et.al. [5] proposes soil moisture sensors, LDR sensors, and DHT11 sensors for monitoring. Data from all of these sensors is collected and given for processing by module. Based on data computation, a system manages factors such as pump, turbines, ventilation and lighting. The HTTP protocol is used to connect the Micro Controller module to the wireless LAN. The intelligent agriculture model that has been proposed by the authors aid in productivity growth and scientific farming. This technology-based agricultural strategy is a successful model.

Uday, et.al. [6] proposes automatic water pipe valve ON and OFF system. This system works based on data retrieved from sensors which was fixed in irrigation field. Soil moisture detector were placed in different places by creating blocks in the agricultural land. This system works effectively in rainy season and regulates production by consuming less water. IoT system is used to control water valve as well as protection system. Based on findings, proposed technology offers a solution for automatic greenhouse irrigation system.

Sujin J. S, et.al. [7] proposed a management system using the Internet of Things (IoT) for plant nursery. This mechanism monitor factors like humidity, soil saturation, temperature, closeness to fire and light intensity. User can monitor required parameters on his desktop or mobile device. Node MCU model is used for transferring data to mobile phone and desktop. Proposed technique reduces Physical and human intervention. System proposed by the authors can be utilized in plant fields, nurseries and home or terrace garden.

PROPOSED MODEL

A Greenhouse control system is proposed with Node MCU ESP8266 module for controlling and regulating climatic factors like light intensity, humidity, air temperature and pesticides. Each category regulates a different parameter. Overview of the proposed system is as shown in the Fig. 1. The Node MCU module receives data from all of the sensors and processes it. The IoT user interface is used as the component expression to manually enter the value for various parameters.

Fig. 1. System Overview

Monitoring and Controlling Systems
Monitoring System

A range of specialized sensors which includes the DHT11 temperature and humidity sensor, ground moisture sensor, LDR light sensor, and PIR pesticide detection help sensor were employed inside for monitoring various parameters for greenhouse maintenance system.

Controlling System

This system includes a special device that controls parameters in line with the ideal environmental conditions for the plant inside the nursery to bloom. Various controlling system employed were

- Temperature and Humidity manipulation mechanism: It is beneficial to keep the greenhouse ventilated at certain temperature.
- Soil moisture control system: Proper irrigation system can bring control on moisture level in the soil which helps optimized growth of plants.
- Light controlling system: This system employs controlling the light intensity required for the plant growth. Carbon emission is drastically reduced by having proper lightning system.

MODULES

Node MCU ESP8266

Node MCU module [1, 2] has a ESP8266 microcontroller chip designed for low power consumption. Its Wi – Fi system on Chip SoC enables connection with cloud internet. This compact module includes PCB antenna for wireless connectivity shown in Fig. 2. Hardware includes 64 KB SRAM with 4 MB Flash memory works within operating voltage 3.3 volts.

Fig. 2. Node MCU ESP8266

Fig. 3. DHT11 Temperature and Humidity Sensor

DHT 11 Temperature and Humidity Sensor

This sensor [8] works with negative temperature coefficient, that is NTC for temperature measurement and it has microcontroller to send the temperature value as an 8-bit data through single serial port pin. It works with the supply ranges from 3.5 volts to 5.5 volts. It senses temperature from as low as 0 degree to and as high upto 50 degree. Fig. 3 is the sensor to measure temperature also senses humidity ranges from 20 to 90 percentage with 1 percent tolerance. It consumes lower power in idle cases and after MCU start signal it switches to running mode. This DHT11 is a low cost device.

Soil Moisture Sensor

Robotbanao SMS operates on the principle of a battery, which combines two electrodes to assess the inductance and dielectric properties of various materials. RK510 sensors works by frequency domain reflectometry method to measure volumetric water content in the soil. Depending on the local temperature and humidity, the sensor accumulates and the fabric's dielectric voltage combined determines the strength of the soil sample. It has 4 pins, power supply and ground take 2 pins and others for analog as well as digital output serial pins shown in the Fig. 4. Any values less than 370 defines sensor is fully in water or almost mud. Values ranges from 370 to 600 defines soil is humid in nature. This value defines water requirement is sufficient for plantation. Soil is dry and it need water can be concluded when the value is more than 600 and upto 1000. Any value more than 1000 shows sensor is disconnected.

Fig. 4. Soil Moisture Sensor

Fig. 5. LDR Sensor

LDR Sensor

Light dependent resistor works as negative resistance with respect to light that is as light intensity increases its resistance decreases. Cadmium Sulphide (CdS) semiconductor is coated material works as photoconductivity medium. It has maximum of few Kilo Ohms in darkness and its resistivity decreases with light intensity. LDR sensor module as in the Fig. 5 has LM393 comparator with variable resistor. It has ground, supply pins and 2 more for analog and digital output.

PIR Sensor

It is Passive Infrared (PIR) sensor module's [9] adjustable sensitivity enables the detection of diverse movements at distances ranging from 3 to 7 meters. A visual tool as shown in Fig. 6 called (PIR) HC – SR501 is made to reach these IR distances while an insect, animal or person is nearby. to use a straightforward lens to access a wider range of content. At the building's entryway, PIR movement sensors have been installed. As previously mentioned, these senses accidentally come across human behavior. We are now successfully able to receive notifications on our IoT platform if there is an internal extrusion of PIR sensor fame.

Fig. 6. Passive Infrared Sensor (PIR)

Fig. 7.

Flow graph of Code

Software Section

Arduino IDE version 1.8.18 is Arduino open source software which we use to load our program in the board [10]. Flow graph of the code is presented in Fig. 7, Pin and values were initialized and serial output of the sensor is feed to the processing unit. This program runs on several platforms such as Windows, MACOS, or Linux. This part gives information about the software used in this program to integrate the operating system. With this, we can define the various values of the system parameter given and load the program into the Node MCU ESP8266 module to carry out the operation.

The IDE is provided by the Arduino community itself and it is a cross-platform software which provides portability that can run on multiple operating environments. Compiling of code with this software is simple and also can be uploaded to an Arduino board without major issues. Node MCU is the core processing unit which take input from all sensors. Based on the initialized values for different plants we get corresponding output to the controlling unit. This controlling units controls various systems like water, light and pesticides. Wi – Fi Output also connected to IoT platform and the same gets displayed in display devices.

In practical the monitored values output was received as shown in Fig. 8 through ThingSpeak™. As discussed in the flow graph we predefine the required humidity from air, moisture from soil, temperature of the surroundings and presence of animals or insects in the environment values of different plants from the Table I in ESP8266. Real world values were measured 24 hours and 365 days by all sensors continuously and fed into processing unit. Based on predefined result output from Node MCU controls different valve such as water, pesticide and light. Through this mechanism have continuous monitoring system and same will be displayed to mobile of the farmers or proprietor of the plant nursery.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Plant nursery or home garden can have controlled greenhouse nature, based on performance of our module. On implementation of this module and based on normalized and predefined vales of certain crops we have succeeded in continuous monitoring system without human intervention. Based on the existing greenhouse parameter [11] and by farmer’s statement we have Table I of reference for the few plants and the same is reference and threshold for the controlling units.

Table I. Normalized Greenhouse Parameter

	Temperature	Relative Humidity	Soil Moisture
Beans	19 ^o to 27 ^o	70	24
Tomato	19.5 ^o to 28 ^o	68	22
Cabbage	18 ^o to 23 ^o	73	22
Potato	18 ^o to 25 ^o	68	21

7.1 ThingSpeak™

MathWorks® gives an open platform called ThingSpeak™ for IoT data visualization and analysis. It displays data obtained from sensors as a live streaming as shown in Fig. 8 from cloud. Installation of sensors where done in Node MCU and appropriate header file were included for sensors. Wi-Fi credential were created and live data can be visualized for each sensor. Data gets refreshed in the display that is updated once in every 15 to 20 seconds [12].

Fig. 8. Graphs in ThingSpeak™

Based on initialization for each sensor continuous live data on hourly basis can be viewed and also for day wise view. From Field 1 chart for temperature it is observed that temperature drops at certain point and the control systems maintains the steady temperature by proper exhaust system. From Field 2 chart for humidity we conclude system maintains and retain steady relative humidity by proper blow of water droplets. Field 3 chart depicts the variation in soil moisture content and how control system stabilizes the same for proper Greenhouse environment.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

In this study, low-cost Node MCU ESP8266 for thermal farm monitoring and management has been created. Its online

operations are managed and coordinated by the model. With a Wi-Fi connection, time is more adaptable and effective. Moreover, it decreases the number of employees at the same time. The efficient compliance and control of a system with pertinent data have been demonstrated by its successful operation. Records from the camps and prompt suggestions from the senses speed up reliability.

This proposed smart farming can be highly beneficial for improving productivity and practicing clinical farming. Consequently, this kind of farming must be carried out for less consumption of water and electricity for controlled environment to have greenhouse. By proper case study this system can be extend for perennial crops such as coffee, grapes and berries. The same system can also extend with shelf life calculation by artificial intelligence methods for fruit producing trees.

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